

A STUDY TO FIND THE REASONS FOR POOR ACADEMIC RESULT AMONG STUDENTS IN DHANALAKSHMI SRINIVASAN ENGINEERING COLLEGE, PERAMBALUR

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Abstract:

This project titled as A Study to Find the Reasons for Poor Academic Result among Students in Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College, Perambalur focuses on reasons for poor academic performance of students. The sample size for this study is 250. The research design carried out for this study is descriptive types of research. Primary data are collected from the respondents of various department students through a structured undisguised questionnaire. Statistical tool like graphs, internal estimation, chi-squared test and correlation have been used for the purpose of analysis. The findings of the study were arrived based on analysis conducted. Some of the major findings of the study relate to increase necessity of having respondents by Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College, Perambalur. The study have been concluded that the performance of Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College, Perambalur is excellent in comparison with its another college and that the college has high growth prospects in future years to come.

Key Words: Reasons for Poor Academic Result, Action Taken By Management and Psychological Attitude of Students.

Introduction:

College life can be nerve-racking, although it is without doubt one of the most unforgettable experiences in one's life. It corresponds an important develop moral stage for both late teenagers and young adults. College Students deal with so many hardships and there are many circumstances that make it harder to concentrate with school and to have a sense of balance in their daily lives. Every college student knows it is important to be able to perform their best in school in order to obtain a great education. It is the little things that seem to contribute in which they end up affecting a college student's academic performance.

Review Literature:

Farely and Rosnow (1975) studied the responsible factors for schooling. The responsible factors for schooling were found to be, to learn, to prepare for later life and the future and to get the job.

Parikh P A (1978) A Study of achievement motivation, school performance and educational norms of secondary, school, pupils. The study revealed that the pupils of English medium schools had more achievement oriented ideas than the pupils of Gujrati Medium Schools. (ii) Educational norms regarding achievement related perception and belief were significantly related to achievement motivation of Bombay school pupils.

Objectives of the Study:

- To analyse the reason for poor academic result of students.
- To analyse and action taken by the college to improve the poor academic result of the students.
- To analyse the student psychological impact towards poor academic result.

Research Design:

A study was carried out with the descriptive type of research. Descriptive research is used to describe characteristics of a population or phenomenon being studied.

Sampling Design:

1	Sampling Technique	Simple Random Sampling
2	Sample Size	250
3	Population	2272
4	Sample Area	Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College, Perambalur

Tools for Data Collection:

Primary data: The primary data was obtained by questionnaire method.

Statistical Tools Used:

- Percentage Method
- Chi-square test
- Correlation
- ANOVA test

Research Methodology:

Research methodology is a systematic process of solving the research problem. It may be understood as role conflict among the students, how research is done scientifically. The method adopted the data, were questionnaire with direct survey.

Data Analysis and Interpretation:

Classification of Doubt from Teacher

S.No	Particulars	No. of Respondents	% of Respondents
1	Strongly Satisfy	53	21
2	Satisfy	100	40
3	Neutral	49	20
4	Dissatisfy	26	10
5	Strongly Dissatisfy	22	9
	Total	250	100

Classification of Doubt from Teacher:

Correlation Method 1:

Table showing the relationship between the satisfaction towards the clarification of doubt and attitude of staff towards the academic result.

The Satisfaction Towards the Clarification of Doubt	53	100	49	26	22	240
Attitude of Staff Towards the Academic Result	74	47	63	39	27	240

$$r_{xy} = \frac{n\sum XY - (\sum X)(\sum Y)}{\sqrt{n(\sum X^2) - (\sum X)^2} \cdot \sqrt{n(\sum Y^2) - (\sum Y)^2}}$$

Answer:

$$r_{xy} = 0.3504$$

Inference:

There is high positive correlation between the Satisfaction towards the clarification of doubt and attitude of staff towards the academic result.

Suggestions:

Learn to have a positive attitude towards learning. Students must take short breaks in between the study. Make learning fun. Ask questions to the staff about the portions taken in class. Pay more attention in class. Start organizing your work in a better manner. This will reduce overload of work.

Conclusion:

In this paper, we discussed a brief summary of research as stated, need, significance, importance, assumptions, objectives, operational definitions, scope, limitations, research design, method of research used for the present study, population, sample, methods of sampling, size of the sample, procedure of data collection and statistical techniques, findings and conclusions of the research. The study is conducted for providing solutions for dealing with academic failure. Academic result is a factor for measuring students learning skills and also knowledge. Hence, the researcher has provided many suggestions for improving student's academic performance.

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